

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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BARRIERS AND FACILITATORS TO HPV VACCINATION AMONG
COMMUNITY COLLEGE STUDENTS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this project was to identify facilitators and barriers to human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccine among community college students as a quality improvement study. The study used the Health Belief Model as the framework guiding this research. Data were collected using a paper and pencil survey given to students seeking services at a community college student health center. Thirty-seven subjects were included in the study. Data provided in the confidential surveys revealed that demographic data and health behaviors were not significant predictors of HPV vaccine status. The most influential predictor of vaccine status was information or a recommendation from the healthcare provider.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vi
LIST OF FIGURES.....	vii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS.....	viii
BACKGROUND.....	1
Needs Assessment and Problem Statement.....	1
Purpose.....	3
Research Questions.....	4
Supporting Framework.....	5
REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....	8
Introduction.....	8
Cervical Cancer.....	8
HPV as a Sexually Transmitted Infection.....	9
Acceptance of the HPV Vaccine.....	9
Fiduciary Concerns.....	11
METHODS.....	13
Protection of Human Rights.....	14
Procedure.....	14
Survey Development Validity and Reliability.....	14
Ethical Considerations.....	16
Data Analysis.....	16
RESULTS.....	18
DISCUSSION.....	27
Limitations.....	28
Recommendations and Project Dissemination.....	29
REFERENCES.....	31

APPENDIX A: INFORMED CONSENT	35
APPENDIX B: SURVEY	37
APPENDIX C: IRB APPROVAL	40

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Basic Demographics of Survey Sample.....	22
2. Vaccination Status by Sample Demographic Characteristics	23
3. Health Behaviors by Vaccination Status.....	24
4. HPV Knowledge by Vaccination Status	25
5. Thematic Comments From 31 Study Subjects.....	26

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Conceptual model for HPV vaccine compliance using the Health Belief Model.....	7

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BACKGROUND

Needs Assessment and Problem Statement

There are 20 million people currently living with the human papillomavirus (HPV) in the United States. There are 6 million new infections occurring annually, making HPV the most prevalent of all sexually transmitted infections (STI; American Sexual Health Association, 2013). Approximately 80% of sexually active individuals will contract the virus at some point in their lives (Markowitz et al., 2007). Even though HPV is considered a sexually transmitted infection, the virus is also transmitted from skin to skin contact and can be transferred without intercourse. Consistent use of condoms can decrease the spread of HPV, but because there are areas of skin not protected, HPV can still be transmitted (National Institutes of Health, 2013). Therefore, barrier methods are not totally effective and may not protect against HPV infection; however, a vaccination is available that offers excellent protection (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2009).

The two vaccines available to prevent HPV infection are Gardasil and Cervarix (Katz, Capu, & Bocchini, 2012). The Food and Drug Association (FDA) has approved Gardasil for use in females ages 9-26. Gardasil helps to protect against cancer of the cervix, vagina, and vulva. Gardasil also protects against warts in the anal and genital region. Gardasil is approved for males ages 9-26 for the prevention of genital warts and anal cancer. Cervarix was FDA approved for use in females ages 10-25 to protect against cancer of the cervix (Edgar, 2011). Both vaccines are 100% effective in the prevention of high grade cervical intraepithelial neoplasias and adenocarcinomas (CDC, 2013).

Furthermore, Gardasil has virtually 100% efficacy against the HPV strains that cause genital warts (CDC, 2013).

The Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices (ACIP) recommends routine vaccination for all females ages 11 and 12, with catch-up for those ages 13 to 26 years who have not previously been vaccinated (CDC, 2010). For males, ACIP guidelines recommend routine vaccination at ages 11 and 12, with catch-up for males ages 13-21 who have not received the vaccine. Males 22 through 26 years of age may be vaccinated if they have sex with men, are immunocompromised, or test positive for human immunodeficiency virus (CDC, 2013). Studies on the efficacy of Gardasil in women who are older than 26 years of age are currently being conducted. Because these studies are still in the trial phase, the ACIP does not recommend the use of this vaccine outside the FDA licensing guidelines.

The HPV vaccines are recommended for use in adolescents prior to sexual debut because immunogenicity is higher in younger girls (Ratanasiripong, 2012). Despite the simplicity of dosing, the compliance for this cancer preventing vaccination is at an alarming low rate. Ratanasiripong (2012) reported in a systematic review that for women ages 19 to 26, only 17.1% had received at least one dose of an HPV vaccine. Forty-four percent of adolescent females ages 13 to 17 received at least one dose but only 26.7% received all three doses of the HPV vaccine (Ratanasiripong, 2012). The CDC (2012) reported that the three-dose HPV vaccination rate in the United States for adolescent girls ages 13-17 in 2011 was 34.8%.

The CDC (2013) estimated that 8 billion dollars are spent annually on direct medical costs for HPV-associated diseases. The majority of the cost, 82%, is attributed

to cervical cancer, while 12% is attributed to oropharyngeal and anal cancers, 4% on diagnoses and treatment of genital warts, and 2% is spent on treatment of recurrent respiratory papillomatosis (Chesson et al., 2012). Indirect costs related to lack of productivity and primary care issues are difficult to quantify. Additionally, psychosocial costs of embarrassment, shame and guilt are likely experienced by most of those who are diagnosed with HPV. As a result, these psychosocial issues can lead to additional financial costs as well as a decreased immune function (Kahn et al., 2007).

The HPV vaccine is effective in addressing both the financial burden of increasing health care costs and in decreasing the morbidity and mortality of HPV associated diseases (Armstrong, 2010). With healthcare reform, the vaccines for HPV are now available for all regardless of ability to pay; therefore, cost is no longer an issue for patients to not receive this life saving immunization (Healthcare.gov, 2010). Providers need to offer this immunization and educate their patients appropriately about its benefits so that cervical cancer can be greatly reduced or possibly eradicated.

Given the potential impact HPV vaccination has on overall health, an understanding of the barriers to its use, aside from the ability to pay, will likely improve the vaccination rate. The factors that facilitated students to request the HPV vaccine and the barriers that prevented students from receiving the HPV vaccine need to be identified. Preventing the cancers that are caused by HPV is essential due to the high prevalence of HPV in sexually active individuals.

Purpose

Thus the purpose of this study was to describe existing barriers and facilitators to HPV vaccination among a select group of community college students in Southern

California and to explore their knowledge level regarding HPV vaccination. This information will be used for quality improvement purposes at a community college student health center to increase HPV vaccination rates. The findings from this study will assist health center staff in providing patient education on HPV and HPV vaccine in the hope of increasing the understanding of the disease and the uptake of the vaccine in the community college population.

Research Questions

There were both qualitative and quantitative research questions addressed in this doctoral project. The qualitative research questions sought self-report information from subjects about their decision making process related to HPV vaccine. It was hoped that answers to the following open-ended questions would provide knowledge of factors that would help to increase the HPV immunization uptake rates. The qualitative research questions were:

1. What factors influenced students to complete the series of vaccines against the HPV?
2. What factors influenced students to have partially completed the series of vaccines against the HPV?
3. What factors influenced students to decide against not beginning the series of immunizations against the HPV?

The quantitative research questions that were investigated in order to increase the HPV immunization uptake rates were:

4. What demographic factors were associated with students who completed the series of vaccines against the HPV?

5. What demographic factors were associated with students who only partially completed the series of vaccines against the HPV?
6. What demographic factors were associated with students who decided against the series of vaccines against the HPV?

The health behaviors of the students were also investigated to see if there was a correlation between high risk behaviors and:

7. Students who completed the series of vaccines against the HPV?
8. Students who only partially completed the series of vaccines against the HPV?

Supporting Framework

There are a multitude of theories, beliefs, and models that are used as underpinnings of studies that seek to explain the healthcare behaviors of individuals. Such frameworks are attempts to formulate proper interventions and or education plans to better the health and healthcare behaviors of individuals. The Health Belief Model (HBM) is a psychological model developed in the 1950s by social psychologists Hochbaum, Rosenstock, and Kegels (Rosenstock, 1966). The HBM postulates that a person will engage in a preventative action if the benefit of that action will result in preventing the negative effect if that action is not taken (Rosenstock, 1966). There are six concepts inherent to the HBM: perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, perceived benefits, perceived barriers, cues-to action and self-efficacy (Rosenstock, 1966). Although not directly stated the main theme of the HBM is health motivation. This seamlessly agrees with the goal of completion of the vaccine for HPV as a preventative measure against cervical cancer and genital warts.

The health belief conceptual model was applied as the framework in this study seeking to identify facilitators to improve vaccination compliance in community college students (see Figure 1). The student receives education about HPV and the HPV vaccine (perceived susceptibility). The student learns that HPV can cause conditions from genital warts to cancer in both males and females (perceived severity). The student is informed that the HPV vaccine is recommended for males and females ages 9-26 years, because it can prevent the most common types of genital warts and cancer (perceived benefits). The student learns that the vaccine has few side effects, and is given free at the student health center (perceived barriers). The student goes to the student health center to begin the series of injections for the HPV vaccine (cue to action and self-efficacy).

Figure 1. Conceptual model for HPV vaccine compliance using the Health Belief Model.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Introduction

The purpose of this study was to identify whether health behaviors, demographic factors and/or other issues are preventing college age students from accessing and completing the HPV vaccine series. If significant variables can be identified that are linked to whether a person is more or less likely to attain the HPV vaccine, then knowledge of these factors can be utilized in educational plans to increase uptake of the vaccine. Providers need to do more than offer this vaccine; they need to educate their patients appropriately so that the rate of cervical cancer can be greatly reduced or possibly eradicating this cause of cancer. In addition genital warts and the other negative consequences of HPV can and will be diminished. Thus this review of literature covers cervical cancer, HPV, the acceptance of the vaccine for HPV, fiduciary concerns and the framework of the HBM.

Cervical Cancer

Cervical cancer is the second most common form of cancer in women worldwide (Shiffman, Castle, Jeromino, Rodriquez, & Wacholder, 2007). Studies support that cervical cancer is caused by high-risk HPV genotypes (Castle et al., 2009; CDC, 2009; Kjaer, Frederiksen, Munk, & Iftner, 2010). These same high-risk HPV types are responsible for vaginal, vulvar, and anal cancers (CDC, 2010). Shiffman et al. (2007) reported 80% of cervical cancers worldwide were in Westernized countries where women have the benefits of screening tests for identification and prevention of HPV through vaccines. Noteworthy, in the United States there has been a decline in the number of young adult females initiating Papanicolaou (PAP) smears (Roland et al., 2013). A PAP

smear is performed during a pelvic exam and is a screening test for cervical cancer. The cervix is scraped and the cells are looked at for abnormalities. Further testing such as a biopsy and or colposcopy may be performed based of the results of the PAP smear.

HPV as a Sexually Transmitted Infection

Human papillomavirus is the most prevalent STI. Approximately 79 million Americans are currently infected with at least one genotype of HPV. It is so prevalent that virtually all sexually-active individuals will become infected with HPV at some point in their lives (Dilsa et al., 2012). This means that virtually all sexually active individuals are at risk of acquiring the adverse consequences of HPV infection. Although HPV is considered a STI, it is transmitted by skin to skin contact and can be spread without having sexual intercourse and even with the use of a condom (CDC, 2010). Many individuals who are infected with the HPV virus have no visible symptoms, and, as a result, nearly 50% of sexually active people are infected at any given point of time (CDC, 2010). Studies have shown that as high as 80% of all sexually active individuals will be infected with HPV at some point in their lives (CDC, 2012). Fortunately up to 90% of the cases of HPV infection can be cleared by the body's immune system within 2 years (CDC, 2010). However, persistent infection over many years is linked to the progression of cervical dysplasia and malignancy (Kjaer et al., 2010).

Acceptance of the HPV Vaccine

The vaccines for HPV can prevent infection from the most high risk genotypes of HPV; however, the number of individuals who have chosen to receive the vaccine is far below the desired level (CDC, 2012). The vaccine for HPV, Gardasil, was approved in 2006 for females and for males in 2009. In 2010, the CDC recommended this

immunization be given to boys and girls beginning at age 9 (Bartlett & Peterson, 2011). Because immunization practices for HPV have shown 100% efficacy in the prevention of the genotypes that cause the high-grade cervical intraepithelialneoplasias and adenocarcinomas, acceptance of the immunization is the ultimate public health goal for all adolescents (Brotherton & Mullins, 2012). The completion of the vaccine requires a total of three doses over a 6-month period. Studies are in progress to demonstrate the efficacy of a double dose or single dose series as compared to the three vaccinations currently recommended (Moon, 2013).

National endorsement studies have shown that less than 25% of those who initiate the series complete the three required doses of the HPV vaccine to assure adequate protection against HPV related diseases. In contrast tetanus, diphtheria, and pertussis (Tdap) and Meningococcal Conjugate Vaccine (MCV4) coverage is on the increase, more than double that of the increase for the HPV vaccine. In the United States, the coverage for girls who received at least one dose of HPV vaccine increased to 53.0% in 2011, and for all three doses it increased to 34.8%. Therefore 29% of the females in 2011 did not complete their HPV vaccination series. The number of boys who received at least one dose of HPV vaccine increased to 8.3% and for all three doses the rate was 1% (CDC, 2012). The Meningococcal Conjugate Vaccine (MCV4) and Gardasil were approved within a year of each other; however, the coverage for MCV4 is 63% compared to 34% for HPV coverage in females (CDC, 2012).

The rationale often given for disparity in all vaccine coverage rates is a lack of access to health care for lower income families and minorities. In reality the initiation and completion rates of the HPV vaccine is higher in Hispanics and Blacks than in

Caucasians. Similarly higher rates are demonstrated in families living below the poverty level than those living at or above the poverty level.

Health care providers who do not identify patients who are eligible for the vaccines or do not use reminder systems available in their electronic medical records are missing an opportunity to increase HPV vaccine compliance (Phillips, 2011). With less than universal acceptance of this preventative health measure, it is imperative that health care providers discover what influences a woman or man to decide to take the preventative HPV vaccination series to completion or even to begin the vaccination series (Bartlett & Peterson, 2011; Bennett, Buchanan, & Adams, 2012; Ratanasiripong, 2012). Studies have shown that race and income may be factors; however, research demonstrated that the most influential factor for an individual initiating the vaccine series is the health care provider providing education and recommending the vaccine (Malouf, Hendriksz, & Foy, 2012).

Fiduciary Concerns

In the United States, more than \$3.5 billion is spent annually on follow-up for abnormal pap smears (Dempsey & Freed, 2008). As previously mentioned according to Chesson et al. (2012), the annual direct medical cost burden of diagnosing and treating HPV-associated disease is an estimated \$8 billion; however, these expenditures represent only the direct medical costs and do not include additional expenses for time missed from school or work. The World Health Organization (WHO), United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), and the World Bank came up with the term DALY for disability-adjusted life years. DALY combine the years of life lost due to premature death (mortality) and loss of full health due to illness and disability (morbidity). Immunizations for vaccine

preventable diseases were identified as one avenue that would decrease a DALY disease burden score (Armstrong, 2010). Many studies have shown that the administration of the HPV vaccines would help not only financially but also would decrease the incidence of cervical cancer (Chesson et al., 2012; Kjaer et al., 2010). As of September 2010, The Affordable Care Act requires insurance companies to cover HPV immunizations without charging a deductible, copayment or coinsurance. Irrespective of the benefits of the HPV vaccine the uptake of the vaccine has been below the anticipated levels (Dempsey, Shaffer, & Cohn, 2012; Manhart et al., 2011). The ACIP noted that recommendations alone for adolescents to receive the vaccinations for HPV have not been enough to increase the acceptance of the HPV vaccine in the United States. It is crucial that providers have a better understanding of the dynamic forces underlying the low acceptance rate of this preventative vaccine (Chan, Chan, Ng, & Wong, 2012; Dempsey & Mendez, 2010; Manhart et al., 2011; Rosenthal, Weiss, Zimet, Good, & Vichnin, M, 2011).

METHODS

The purpose of this study was to outline existing facilitators and barriers to HPV vaccinations among a group of local community college students and to examine their level of awareness regarding HPV and the HPV vaccine. Thus an exploratory research design was used to collect data related to motivating factors to either seek or not seek HPV vaccination.

A convenience sample comprised of all students seeking care at a community college student health center from November 6, 2013 through February 14, 2014 was the focus of this project. Each student was handed the consent form (Appendix A) and a study survey (Appendix B) by the registered nurse (RN) or nurse practitioner (NP) on duty. The RN or NP asked the student to read the consent form that described the study to decide whether to participate in the study. All students were given the consent form and questionnaire regardless of age or gender. Demographic information as well as information regarding HPV and the HPV vaccine was collected in the survey. The information obtained from the participants was used to provide data to the student health center staff to allow a comprehensive approach involving providers and patients in achieving increased student HPV vaccine compliance rates. At the time of data collection this community college had an enrollment of 25,000 students and saw approximately 100 students a week in the student health center. A total of 63 surveys were turned in by students.

Protection of Human Rights

This study, consent form, and the survey tool were reviewed and approved by the student health center administration as well as the CSULB Institutional Review Board Committee (Appendix C).

Procedure

Paper and pen/pencil surveys were confidential and there was no identifiable information on the survey to the student. The student was told to place the completed survey into an envelope labeled "Survey" and then drop it into a secure ballot-type box in the student health center until picked up by the researcher. They were also asked to place the signed consent in an envelope and drop it into a secure ballot-type box. Nurses employed in the student health center of the community college, in which this survey was conducted had a great deal of experience with surveys and were familiar with IRB procedures related to the protection of human rights.

Survey Development Validity and Reliability

The survey was developed to meet the objectives of the study (Appendix B). The researcher designed the survey based on findings from the review of the literature discussed previously and scientific information about HPV and the HPV vaccine. Questions were constructed to identify the student's knowledge of HPV and the HPV vaccine. The survey was also designed to identify health behaviors that could potentially be utilized in planning patient education about HPV and the HPV vaccine. The questions regarding use of condoms, tobacco, alcohol and number of sexual partners asked about risk taking behaviors and were included to incorporate the health belief model construct of perceived vulnerability. Demographic information was also collected. Narrative

responses to open ended questions were solicited regarding information about understanding barriers and facilitators of HPV vaccine acceptance.

The survey was given to five Advance Practice Women's Health Nurse Practitioners to review for accuracy and validity of content and to critique for completeness related to the topic of facilitators and barriers to HPV vaccination. The nurse practitioners had an average of 18 years of experience in the women's health field and had 12 years' experience as educators in a Bachelor of Science Nursing (BSN) pre-licensure program. There was 100% agreement on all questions as to their appropriateness of content to the topic of facilitators and barriers to HPV vaccination. Suggestions were taken and the following two questions were added to the survey as a result of their input: "Have you ever had sex," and "Did you use a condom with your last sexual activity?" There were no questions removed, and no rewording was needed as a result of their critiquing.

A pilot test of the survey was conducted with 13 college-age individuals to test reliability. The students were also asked for their feedback about the consent form and the survey regarding understandability and clarity of the forms. The feedback that was given to this researcher regarding clarity of wording and understandability of the survey was a suggestion made by several of the students to change wording from "engage in" to "had" for some questions. This suggestion to change the "engage in" wording was accepted as it did not alter the overall content of the survey.

The survey was given to the pilot students twice to determine test-retest reliability. They were asked to complete it and then 24 hours later they were asked to take the survey again. The surveys were passed out to the students with a number 1

through 13 written at the top of the form; they were told to review the demographic questions asked in the survey but were told not to fill them out so there would be no identifiable material related to the students on the surveys. The following day the students were given only the surveys and were asked to put the number of the first survey at the top of the second survey. Answers were compared to test for reliability. There was 100% consistency for all test items for all 13 pilot subjects in matching the answers on the surveys from the first day to 24 hours later.

Ethical Considerations

There was no penalty if a student chose not to take part in the survey. There was no penalty for partially filled out surveys. No student was pressured to participate in the survey. The informed consent (Appendix A) was signed prior to completion of the survey. The signed consent was kept separate from the completed survey. There were separate ballot boxes for the completed survey and signed consent to be deposited; so no information provided on the survey would be able to be identifiable and all surveys remained completely anonymous and confidential.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were utilized to analyze the demographic data to investigate possible links with students who completed the series of HPV immunizations; the students who only partially completed the series of vaccines against the HPV; and the students who decided against the series of HPV vaccines. Descriptive statistics were also used to determine whether demographic characteristics were factors in the student's awareness of HPV and HPV vaccines. Chi-Square and *t*-tests were used for statistical

analysis to determine whether demographic characteristics were related to intention to be vaccinated against cervical cancer. Significance levels were set at < 0.05 .

RESULTS

The research focused on identifying barriers and facilitators to HPV vaccine through survey collection among a convenience sample of community college students coming into the student health center that served as the setting for this study. The survey was given to students in the community college's student health center from November 6, 2013 to December 16, 2013 and again from January 26, 2014 to January 26, 2014 due to winter break for the campus. There were a total of 63 surveys returned. Data from 37 fully completed surveys were used; 26 surveys had missing data and were not analyzed as part of the study. The basic demographics of the 37 subjects are listed in Table 1.

The mean age of the 37 respondents was 22 years, with a range from 18 to 39 years. There were 28 female (76%) and nine males (24%) who participated. One participant (3%) was married, one (3%) widowed, one in a domestic partnership, one (3%) engaged, and the remaining 34 (91%) considered themselves never married and single. There were 18 (49%) subjects who considered themselves White; 11 (30%) were Asian Pacific/Islander; six (16%) were Hispanic/Latino; one (3%) was African/American/Black; and one (3%) indicated multicultural. Reported income ranged from less than \$9,999 to \$39,999, with the majority (21 or 57%) earning less than \$9,999 annually. There were 15 (41%) Christians, eight (22%) Roman Catholic, one (3%) Mormon, one (3%) atheist, one (3%) Jewish, 3(8%) agnostic, and eight (22%) were without any religious affiliation.

The study investigated whether demographic data were significant predictors of HPV vaccine status. The researcher was interested in answering two questions: What demographic factors were associated with students who completed the series of vaccines

against the HPV? and What demographic factors were associated with students who did not complete the series of vaccines against the HPV? Because of the low percentage of subjects (28%) who had completed or only partially received the full vaccine series against HPV, the data were consolidated to those who were vaccinated against HPV and those who were not vaccinated against HPV. The Chi-Square tests of independence or independent samples *t*-test, where appropriate, were used to compare demographic factors and immunization status. The results indicated no significant relationship between demographic data (age, gender, marital status, race, income and religion) and vaccine compliance (see Table 2).

The next area of interest was to see if the health behaviors of the subjects were a significant indicator of the HPV vaccine acceptance. Subjects were asked about sexual history including a history of oral, anal and vaginal intercourse. They were asked about their use of condoms and history of sexually transmitted infection both personal and partners'. The Chi-Square analysis indicated that the health behaviors were not a significant indicator of HPV vaccine acceptance (see Table 3).

The final area of interest was to determine whether knowledge of HPV and the HPV vaccine affected the subject's acceptance of the vaccine against HPV. The knowledge questions about HPV vaccine queried the subject's understanding that the vaccine is for both males and females and that it is now covered by all insurance companies. The knowledge questions about HPV infection asked about the subject's knowledge of transmission of HPV, the different types/strains of HPV, treatment of genital warts caused by the HPV virus, signs and symptoms of HPV and mode of transmission of HPV. The total score possible for all knowledge questions was 18. The

mean score of those who were not vaccinated, was 2.5 (*SD*, 2.1) with a mean score of 5.6 (*SD*, 1.9) for those who were vaccinated; the mean scores for both groups would be considered low. The Chi-Square tests of independence showed a significant relationship ($p = .001$) between knowledge of HPV and the vaccine against HPV and vaccination status (see Table 4.)

Three open-ended questions were included in the survey, and responses were analyzed by the researcher to determine whether there were themes that could explain the reasons subjects received or did not receive the immunization. Thirty-one out of the total of 37 subjects in the sample provided written responses that were used by the researcher as part of the qualitative analysis of responses. A summary of the subjects' responses is reported in Table 5. Three (43%) of the subjects who had the vaccine said they took it to prevent cervical cancer. Two (29%) of the subjects who had the vaccine said they took it because their provider recommended the vaccine, and one (14%) who had the vaccine took it because it was an immigration requirement. However, hepatitis B vaccine (HBV), not HPV vaccine, is a requirement for immigration. The researcher concluded that this individual may believe he or she is vaccinated against HPV when this is not the case.

Twenty-five of the 37 individuals who responded that they did not have the vaccine provided written responses to the open ended questions. Subjects were instructed to provide as many responses as they desired. Ten of the subjects (40%) said they needed more information to take the vaccine. Ten (40%) said they just did not receive the vaccine and gave no further explanation. Two (8%) of the subjects said they did not receive the vaccine because they did not believe they would ever acquire HPV. One

(4%) just did not want the HPV vaccine; one subject (4%) was worried about side effects of the vaccine; and another one (4%) said his/her parent was against the vaccine.

Table 1

Basic Demographics of Survey Sample (n = 37)

Demographic data		<i>n</i>	%
Age	18	4	11
	19	8	22
	20	5	14
	21	2	7
	22	5	14
	23	2	7
	24	3	8
	26	1	3
	27	1	3
	28	1	3
	29	2	5
	31	1	3
	38	1	3
	39	1	3
Gender	Male	9	24
	Female	28	76
Marital status	Widowed	1	3
	Domestic partnership	1	3
	Engaged	1	3
	Single/never married	34	92
Race/ethnicity	African American/Black	1	3
	Asian Pacific Islander	11	30
	Hispanic Latino	6	16
	Multicultural	1	3
	White	18	49
Income	< \$9,999	21	57
	\$10,000 - \$19,999	1	33
	\$ 20,000 - \$29,999	3	8
	\$30,999 - \$39,000	1	3
Religious affiliation	Christian	15	41
	Roman Catholic	8	22
	Mormon	1	2
	Jewish	1	3
	Agnostic	3	5
	Atheist	1	3
	Other /None	8	22

Table 2

Vaccination Status by Sample Demographic Characteristics

Demographic data	HPV vaccination status ^a		<i>p</i> -value ^b
	Not vaccinated* (<i>n</i> = 30)	Vaccinated* (<i>n</i> = 7)	
Age	23.4 (7.2)	22.6 (4.0)	0.78
Gender			
Male	5 (20.8%)	1 (14.3%)	0.70
Female	19 (79.2%)	6 (85.7%)	
Marital status			
Married/domestic partnership			
Single, never married			
Race/ethnicity ^c			
Non-White			
White			
Income			
< \$9,999			
≥ \$10,000			
Religious ^d			
Yes			
No			

* Reported as Mean (Standard Deviation) or Frequency (Valid Percent) where appropriate.

^a Vaccinated status indicates all three vaccinations were administered. Due to the small number of participants (*n* = 2) reporting partial vaccination (1 or 2 vaccinations), this category was dropped from analyses.

^b Reported for Chi-Square tests of independence or independent samples *t*-test, where appropriate.

^c Non-White Race included African American, Asian, and Hispanic.

^d Included Christian, Roman Catholic, Mormon, Russian Orthodox, and Jewish.

Table 3

Health Behaviors by Vaccination Status (n = 13-37)

Health behavior questions	HPV vaccination status ^a		<i>p</i> -value ^b
	Not vaccinated*	Vaccinated*	
Total score	25 (83.3%)	6 (85.7%)	0.88
Individual questions			
Ever had sex			
Currently sexually activ ³			
Had vaginal sex			
Had anal sex			
Had oral sex			
Use condoms all the time			
Use condoms sometimes			
Use condoms never			
Used condom during last sexual activity			
Diagnosed with STI			
No Hx STI			
Unsure if STI			

* Reported as Frequency “Yes” (Valid Percent “Yes”) where appropriate.

^a Vaccinated status indicates all three vaccinations were administered. Due to the small number of participants ($n = 2$) reporting partial vaccination (1 or 2 vaccinations), this category was dropped from analyses.

^b Reported for Chi-Square tests of independence.

Table 4

HPV Knowledge by Vaccination Status (n = 36-37)

Knowledge questions	HPV vaccination status ^a		<i>p</i> -value ^b
	Not vaccinated*	Vaccinated*	
Total score	2.5 (2.1)	5.6 (1.9)	0.001
Individual questions	6.0 (20.7)	5.0 (71.4)	0.009
Is the immunization for males or females?			
HPV is the most common STI			
There are many types/strains of HPV infections			
HPV related genital warts require medical treatment to go away			
HPV vaccines are covered by all insurance companies			
When someone is infected with HPV there are always visible signs			
It is easy to tell if someone has HPV			
If you use a condom you won't get HPV			
HPV can be spread only through sexual intercourse			

* Reported as Mean (Standard Deviation) or Frequency Correct (Valid Percent Correct) where appropriate.

^a Vaccinated status indicates all three vaccinations were administered. Due to the small number of participants ($n = 2$) reporting partial vaccination (1 or 2 vaccinations), this category was dropped from analyses.

^b Reported for Chi-Square tests of independence or independent samples *t*-test, where appropriate.

Table 5

Thematic Comments From 31 Study Subjects

Reasons for HPV vaccine coverage
Subjects who received full doses of HPV vaccination $n = 7$
Subjects ($n = 6$) responding to this question
<i>To prevent cervical CA = 3 (50%)</i>
Provider recommended $n = 2$ (33%)
Immigration requirement $n = 1$ (17%)
Reasons for lack of vaccine coverage
Sample subjects who did not receive any doses of HPV vaccine $n = 27$
Subjects ($n = 25$) answering this question
<i>Needed more information $n = 10$ (40%)</i>
Just did not receive the vaccine = 10 (40%)
Do not believe they will contact HPV = 2 (8%)
Worried about side effects = 1 (4%)
Did not want = 1 (4%)
Parent against immunization = 1 (4%)

DISCUSSION

Qualitative research questions included in the survey, related to the issue of how to increase the HPV immunization uptake rates were: What factors influenced students to complete the series of vaccines against the HPV? What factors influenced students to have partially completed the series of vaccines against the HPV? Of the 63 subjects responding to the survey, three (0.05%) did not answer questions regarding HPV vaccine status; nine (14%) stated they had all three doses of the vaccines; 33 (52%) stated they had not received the HPV vaccine or had less than the required doses; and 17 (27%) were unsure of their HPV vaccine status. Because of the small sample size and categories with no responses, statistical analysis using Chi-Square tests of independence and independent samples *t*-tests were run on the data from the seven vaccinated and 30 non-vaccinated subjects.

The results of this study align with previous studies conducted to determine factors that influence the decision to begin or the decision against beginning the series of immunizations against the HPV. Studies have consistently demonstrated two factors. First, parental attitudes of pediatric patients played a large role in whether or not a child received the vaccine. Second, when providers recommended the vaccine, compliance was increased (Phillips, 2011; Trim, Nagji, Elit, & Roy, 2011). The data obtained in this study also did not reveal any significant links between demographic variables and compliance in receiving coverage with the HPV vaccine. This study did demonstrate similar results regarding compliance as noted in previous studies with regard to knowledge levels about HPV and the vaccine against HPV. This study revealed a relationship between the knowledge of HPV: the higher the level of knowledge about

HPV, the greater the probability that one was vaccinated against HPV. In addition, the findings of this study found that the amount of knowledge required to increase the compliance of the vaccine against HPV was minimal.

One can conclude from this study that the findings exemplify the need for more education related to HPV and the vaccine against HPV. It is imperative that health care providers implement the Centers for Disease Control and prevention recommendation that HPV vaccine be given to both the pediatric population and those up to age 26 years who need to initiate or catch up on their HPV immunization. By changing this practice among providers and with the 2014 advent of a single dose HPV vaccine being discussed, the acceptance of the HPV vaccine hopefully will increase (Moon, 2013).

Limitations

Almost half (36) of the surveys could not be used for analysis due to missing data (e.g., race), and thus the number of subjects comprising the sample was drastically reduced. This is a common problem in survey research. In addition, because the sample size was small which limits the number of responses (data) in certain categories (e.g., race), this lack of sufficient numbers in a particular category creates problems in analysis with insufficient numbers available for comparison of certain categories. Therefore, all results need to be interpreted with the understanding that many subpopulations in this study, that could be meaningfully different from one another (i.e., Black vs. Asian vs. Hispanic), simply could not be compared using this dataset due to a small sample size in a particular category.

This study used a convenience sample of community college students who came into the student health center for examination; therefore, they may not be comparable to

the general population. Furthermore, the sample consisted of students attending a community college and, therefore, their knowledge of HPV may not be generalizable to the general population of youth. The last note of caution by the researcher involves the method of data collection. This was a pencil and paper survey of self-report given in a student health center, and the subjects' answers may have been biased due to social desirability.

Recommendations and Project Dissemination

The aim of this project was to initiate a quality improvement study to increase HPV vaccine compliance among community college students in a designated student health center. By identifying facilitators and barriers to HPV vaccine compliance, an effective plan for educating community college students who seeks services at their student health center can be formulated. There is increasing information about the perceptions, attitudes, HPV knowledge, and vaccination acceptance and initiation rates of U.S. women, but more research is needed. Acceptance of HPV vaccination was extremely low among the community college students who participated in this exploratory research study. Further studies are needed to identify the sociocultural barriers and motivators to vaccine uptake. Knowledge of the facilitators and barriers identified by specific sociocultural populations will help providers create socioculturally accepted interventions to targeted groups to increase their HPV vaccine uptake. By increasing the number of males and females who are vaccinated against HPV, the number of cases of HPV outbreaks and cancers related to HPV will be decreased.

In order to increase compliance in HPV vaccination rates, healthcare providers must provide educational materials to their patients and be educated about best practices

to change patient behavioral patterns. With growing prospective evidence of vaccine efficacy and safety, it is likely that widespread HPV vaccination can be achieved but will require concerted effort.

The vaccine against HPV was approved by the FDA in 2006 and recommended by the ACIP in 2006 for females ages 11-12, with catch up to age 26, and males ages 11-12 with catch up to 21 years (Edgar, 2011). Students who are 19 years of age should have been fully immunized with the vaccine to prevent HPV. This researcher discovered that was not the case with students coming into the student health center in the community college setting investigated in this study. For unknown reasons many stated they never received information about the vaccine despite the likelihood they had prior healthcare visits. One is then left wondering if HPV vaccine coverage was never discussed at such visits for this target population.

As a result of the study administrators at the health center that was the setting for this study announced plans to start offering HPV vaccine free of charge at the student health center beginning in June of 2014 to all students who need it. During staff meetings, employees of the student health center will be educated about the need for increased education about HPV and the HPV vaccine and the procedures related to offering of the vaccine to students through the health center. Students will also be made aware of HPV and the vaccine against HPV in the college's monthly newsletter. Furthermore this researcher plans to prepare a manuscript for publication and dissemination of the findings to other health care providers.

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APPENDIX A

INFORMED CONSENT

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

(Please read the following very carefully)

A. Introduction and Purpose

You are being asked to participate in a study for a Doctoral Project for the Southern California State University Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) Consortium. The purpose of the study is to identify the reasons community college students either choose to or choose not to be immunized against Human Papillomavirus (HPV) infection. In addition this study explores students' knowledge regarding HPV vaccination. For our purpose, "research" is defined as systematic investigation designed to develop or contribute to general knowledge.

B. Procedure

You will be asked to fill out a survey that asks for information about your opinions on the immunization for HPV and about your sexual health history. You will also be asked demographic information (e.g., gender, age, etc.). This information is for statistical research only. Your name will not be used. Please be honest; there is no wrong answer. (The survey should take approximately 5 minutes)

C. Benefits

The benefits of this study are its ability to describe the existing barriers to HPV vaccinations among community college students and to explore the knowledge level regarding HPV vaccination. This study will help in developing a comprehensive approach, about how to best educate college students about HPV immunization that will involve providers, the patients, and health educators. It is unlikely that you will directly benefit from participation in this study. However, the knowledge gained from this study may contribute to understanding factors that affect your health with regards to HPV and the HPV immunizations.

D. Risks

There are no physical, psychological, or social risks involved in this study. There are no predictable physical ill effects associated with participating in this study. Answering some questions about your health and sexuality might create temporary discomfort. You understand that you are completely free to refuse to answer any question without penalty.

E. Voluntary Participation / Withdrawal

Your participation in this study is completely voluntary. You may discontinue your participation at any time during the study.

F. Compensation/Confidentiality

You will not receive any money for participating in this research.

The survey does not ask for your name. Results will be publicly reported as group averages only.

G. Contact for Questions

If you have any additional questions about the research, your rights, or a research-related injury, you may contact Jill Kardously FNP-BC by e-mail at jkardously@xxx.xxx Margaret Brady RN, B.S.N., M.S., Ph.D., mabrady@Exchange.fullerton.edu

H. Consent to Participate

Your name will not be recorded on the questionnaire and your responses will be anonymous. Again, your participation is voluntary and you may choose to not answer any or all of the questions on the questionnaire even after signing the consent. If you are willing to participate, please sign this form.

Thank you for your assistance.

I have read and understood this consent form, and I agree to participate in this study.

Signature _____

Date _____

APPENDIX B

SURVEY

Questionnaire Statement	Yes	No	Unknown/Unsure
Have you ever heard of Human Papillomavirus HPV?			
Has any Health care Provider ever talked with you about the vaccine to help prevent cervical/anal/rectal or penile cancer?			
Is the immunization against HPV for both males and females?			
Have you ever tested positive for a sexually transmitted infection?			
Have you ever tested positive for HPV or genital warts?			
Do you smoke cigarettes?			(If yes) #packs per day
Have you ever had a Pap smear? (If female)			
Have you had the immunization against HPV (Cervarix or Gardasil)?			
If 'yes' to above, how many doses of the vaccine have you completed?			
Did religious beliefs influence your receiving or not receiving the HPV vaccine?			
Did religious beliefs influence your receiving or not receiving the HPV vaccine?			
Have you ever had an adverse reaction to the vaccine for HPV?			
Do you know anyone who has had an adverse reaction to the vaccine for HPV?			
Have you ever had a friend or family member test positive for HPV or genital warts?			
If you have tested positive for HPV or genital warts, it is too late to get the vaccine?			
Statement about HPV	True	False	Unsure
I am worried about getting HPV or genital warts			
When someone is infected with HPV there are always visible signs.			
HPV is the most common sexually transmitted infection.			
There are many types (strains) of HPV infections.			
It is easy to tell if someone has HPV.			
If you use condoms you won't get HPV.			
HPV can only be spread through sexual intercourse.			
HPV related genital warts require medical treatment to go away.			
HPV vaccines are covered by ALL insurance companies and medical coverage plans.			

SURVEY - continued

Demographics

Sex/Gender:

 Female Male Transgender

Race/Ethnicity:

African American/Black Asian/Pacific Islander Hispanic/Latino
 Multiracial Native American/American Indian White
 Not Listed (please specify) _____

Age: _____ (in years)

Marital Status: What is your marital status?

Currently married Widowed Divorced Separated
 Domestic partnership Engaged Never married/Single

Household Income: What is your total household income? (Do not include parents)

Less than \$9,999 \$10,000 - \$19,999 \$20,000 - \$29,999
 \$30,000 - \$39,999 \$40,000 - \$49,999 \$50,000 - \$59,999
 \$60,000 - \$69,999 \$70,000 - \$79,999 \$80,000 - \$89,999
 \$90,000 - \$99,999 \$100,000 - \$149,999 \$150,000 & >

What is your religious preference?

Christian Roman Catholic Protestant
 Seventh-Day Adventist Mormon Christian Scientist
 Russian Orthodox Greek Orthodox Jewish Muslim
 Agnostic Atheist other (please specify) _____

Please circle your answers

1. Are you currently sexually active?
Yes No
2. Have you ever had sex?
Yes No
3. What type of sex did you have?
Vaginal Anal Oral
4. Have you used condoms in the past?
Always Sometimes Never
5. Did you use a condom with your last sexual activity?
Yes No N/A
6. Have you ever been diagnosed with STI(s) [Sexually Transmitted Infection (STI)]
Yes No
7. Have you ever been treated for an STI(s)
Yes No

8. Has/have your partner(s) ever been diagnosed with STI(s)
Yes No Unknown/Unsure
9. Has/have your partner(s) ever been treated for STI(s)
Yes No Unknown/Unsure
10. Do you smoke cigarettes?
Yes No
11. Do you drink alcohol?
Yes No

What was the reason(s) you did have the immunization against HPV?

What was the reason(s) you did not have the immunization against HPV?

What would (or did) help you remember to receive future doses of the vaccine?

APPENDIX C**IRB APPROVAL**

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LONG BEACH

OFFICE OF RESEARCH & SPONSORED PROGRAMS

DATE: December 4, 2013
TO: Jill Kardously, MSN, BC-FNP
FROM: California State University, Long Beach (IRB)
PROJECT TITLE: [526171-3] Barriers and Facilitators of HPV Vaccine
Among Community College Students
REFERENCE #: 14-095s
SUBMISSION TYPE: Revision
ACTION: APPROVED
APPROVAL DATE: December 4, 2013
EXPIRATION DATE: December 3, 2014
REVIEW TYPE: Administrative

This is to advise you that the Institutional Review Board for the Protection of Human Subjects (IRB) of California State University, Long Beach, has reviewed your protocol application.

Your application is approved. The requested modifications have been received, reviewed, and accepted.

Approval is for a period of one year from the date of this letter and conditional upon your willingness to carry out your continuing responsibilities under University policy. If you would like to continue this research after this one year period, please submit a renewal application and an annual report to the Office of Research & Sponsored Programs two months prior to your expiration date of December 3, 2014.

1. You must clearly indicate in the header or footer of each page of your approved Informed Consent Form the approval and expiration dates of the protocol as follows: **“Approved from December 4, 2013 to December 3, 2014 by the CSULB IRB”**.
2. You are required to inform the Director or Senior Associate Director, Office of Research & Sponsored Programs, in writing (email is acceptable) or through IRBNet within twenty-four hours of any adverse event in the conduct of research involving human subjects. The report shall include the nature of the adverse event, the names of the persons affected, the extent of the injury or breach of security, if any, and any other information material to the situation.
3. You may not change any aspect of your research procedure involving human subjects without written permission from the Director, Office of Research & Sponsored Programs

or the Chair of the IRB. Please use the Protocol Modification Form on IRBNet to request any changes.

4. Maintain your research records as detailed in the protocol.

Should you have any questions about the conduct of your research under this protocol, particularly about providing informed consent and unexpected contingencies, please do not hesitate to call the Office of Research & Sponsored Programs at (562) 985-8147. We wish you the best of success in your research.

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Long Beach Institutional Review Board's records.